

Incomplete list of contributions to Research by by Eberhard R. Hilf, 1963-2022

Eberhard R.Hilf; Oldenburg,Germany; Author Identifications and publication profiles: [ORCID 0000-0002-5910-3819](#); Status: 9.Feb.2022; The content of this text is to be read with care, because of its hidden incompleteness, personal bias, and preference; thus time witnesses are invited to correct and supplement by mailing me relevant information hilf@isn-oldenburg.de ;

Contents

1	Theses online and open access	2
1.1	Theses online and open access	3
2	Management of Online Scientific Information	4
2.1	Online Management of Scientific Information	4
3	Theoretical Physics of atomic clusters	14
3.1	Theoretical Physics of atomic Clusters	14
4	Thermodynamics	16
4.1	Thermodynamics	16
5	Quantum Physics	19
5.1	Quantum Physics	19
6	Mathematics	19
6.1	Mathematics	19
7	Physics of PDMS Plasma Desorption Mass Spectrometry	20
7.1	The Physics of PDMS Plasma Desorption Mass Spectrometry	20
8	Nuclear Physics	24
8.1	Nuclear Physics	24
9	Marine research, offshore sailing	28
9.1	Marine Research, offshore sailing	28
10	Astrophysics	28
10.1	Astrophysics	28
11	Diverses	29
11.1	various contributions	29
12	Diverses	29
12.1	various contributions	29

13 organizing international Conferences and workshops	30
14 academic teaching	30
14.1 Academic Education	30
15 personal documents	30

This (incomplete) list of publications, preprints, conferences organized, scientific projects is to be updated and enriched with summaries of the respective fields with the next versions.

1 Theses online and open access

In 1996 M. Gröetschel ¹ identified the subsection of academic theses and dissertations as an ideal field to pursue the transition of its archives towards Open Access without being blocked by the large commercial publishers.

Thus the *IuK Initiative*^{2, 3} set up a task force which successfully applied for funding by the German Research Foundation: *dissertationen online*, with the partners

Rich activities evolved, on registration process of online theses, Open access posting by local University Libraries using a proposed national standard, archiving by the National Library, tools for enriching scientific information such as how to make use of the Metalanguages PhysML and MathML in HTML documents, reaching an internationally approved metadata set for theses and dissertations, etc.

A set of national workshops was held

In Oldenburg Kerstin Zimmermann⁴ was in charge of setting up and operating an online registry *dissonline*, which listed the links to the University Library Dissertation Repositories.

The real impact of all these activities can be inferred from the number of online open access dissertations in Germany by the National Library, with its steep rise⁵.

¹M.Grötschel, ORCID:0000-0001-8759-6377

²IuK Initiative Information and Communication of the Learned Scientific Societies in Germany

³Information und Kommunikation 2005: Ein Lagebericht und einige Zukunftsperspektiven; Hans-Werner Bierhoff, Joachim Funke, Ulf-Dietrich Reips, Erich Weichselgartner; Psychologische Rundschau (2005), 56, pp. 212-219. <https://doi.org/10.1026/0033-3042.56.3.212>. 2005 Hogrefe Verlag Göttingen

⁴Kerstin Zimmermann; <https://www.physik.org/kerstin/publications.html>

⁵Dissonline and Online Dissertations; German National Library; <https://www.dnb.de/dissonline>

Together with the group of Joachim Schöpfel⁶ Thomas Severiens as the leading scientist of ISN found that the ratio of freely accessible open access dissertations is about 50 per cent of all in both countries, but that the other half has not been registered by the authors online in the local University Library while in France they do, but with embargo of various types.

The lesson is, that dissertations are an important and unique sector of scientific information, but to get them available open access it needs active support, not passively waiting that the author will find the way to the library repository with its rules.

1.1 Theses online and open access

- [al.97] Kerstin Zimmermann et al. *Dissertationen Online, Workflow und Nachweis für Dissertationen*. Dieser Dienst war zeitweise ein Dienst der EPS European Physical Society. 1997. <http://web.archive.org/web/20010201063800/http://www.dissonline.org>.
- [Gon+01] M. Andre Goncalves et al. “MARIAN: Flexible interoperability in a federated digital library of theses and dissertations”. In: *20th World Conference on Open Learning and Distance Education: The Future of Learning - Learning for the Future: Shaping the Transition, ICDE2001*. <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/summary?doi=10.1.1.25.2857> and http://www.dlib.vt.edu/reports/ecdl2001_8.pdf; in 2009 both links did not work; local copy: <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/pub-hilf/10.1.1.25.2857.pdf>. 2001.
- [Sch+14a] J. Schöpfel et al. *E-Dissertations: Access and Restrictions (EDAR) - survey 2014*. Report. 2014. http://archivesic.ccsd.cnrs.fr/sic_01045115.
- [Sch+14b] J. Schöpfel et al. “Restricted vs. open access for electronic theses and dissertations - a challenge for public science”. In: *ETD 2014. 17th International Symposium on Electronic Theses and Dissertations*. Leicester, UK, 2014. <http://www2.le.ac.uk/library/etd2014>.
- [Sch+15] J. Schöpfel et al. “Electronic theses and dissertations: access and restrictions”. In: *D-Lib Magazine* 21 (3/4) (2015).

⁶Joachim Schöpfel, University Lille, France; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4000-807X>

- [K.Z01] K.Zimmermann. “PhysDis – Electronic Dissertations in Physics”. In: ed. by Thorsten Bahne, Thomas Fischer, and Heinrich Stamerjohanns. Program committee: H.J.Becker, E.R.Hilf, G.Toerner. University Duisburg - Essen; DuEPublic 5158, 2001. <https://duepublico.uni-duisburg-essen.de/servlets/DerivateServlet/Derivate-5158/6.hilf.pdf>.

2 Management of Online Scientific Information

2.1 Online Management of Scientific Information

- [BDH91] K. Barghorn, B. Diekmann, and E. R. Hilf. *Einführende Broschüre für die Informationsbeauftragten der Physik-Fachbereiche*. im Auftrag der DPG Deutsche Physikalische Gesellschaft. Oldenburg, 1991.
- [Hil94a] E. R. Hilf. “Integrated Information Management in Physics”. In: *Proceedings of APS E-PRINT Workshop*. Los Alamos, USA: American Physical Society APS, Oct. 14, 1994. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/aps/index.html>.
- [E.R94] E.R.Hilf. *activities in Germany in scientific information management: Frühe Webserver-Liste der Aktivitäten*; <http://elfikom.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/Termine.html>. 1994.
- [Hilb] *Elektronische Fachinformation in der Gegenwart und Zukunft*. April 1994. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/pub-hilf/paper/userguide-1994.pdf>.
- [HW94] E.R. Hilf and L. Weisel. “Dringender Diskussionsbedarf: Wie soll die elektronische Information und Kommunikation in der Physik künftig aussehen”. In: *Physikalische Blätter* 50 (1994). This is the first online article (1994) in the journal (format: html); when the journal was sold to another publisher this original was deliberately dumped. We praise Elsevier-VCH for scanning it in as .pdf., pp. 65–66. ISSN: 1521-3722. DOI: [10.1002/phbl.19940500118](https://doi.org/10.1002/phbl.19940500118). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/phbl.19940500118>.
- [Bar+94] Knut Barghorn et al. *Elektronische Fachinformation in der Gegenwart und in der Zukunft*. Userguide; German. 1994. http://elfikom.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Userguide.Part4/Userguide_html/Userguide_html.html.
- [SHc95] Thomas Severiens, Eberhard R. Hilf, and many coworkers. *PhysNet Physics Network Worldwide: the crew*. 1995. <http://de.physnet.net/PhysNet/crew.html>.
- [DH95] Bernd Diekmann and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Das Werk von Hermann Havekost in den Jahren 1995-2000”. In: 1995. <http://www.bis.uni-oldenburg.de/bisverlag/hv1/43-hilf.pdf>.

- [Hilf] *Neue Wege der wissenschaftlichen Information und Kommunikation*. Programm des gemeinsamen Workshops der vier wissenschaftlichen Fachgesellschaften DMV, DPG, GDCh, GI. Mar. 8, 1995. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/pub-hilf/paper/berlin-1994.pdf>.
- [Hil+96] E.R. Hilf et al. "Integrated Information Management in Physics". In: *The Information Revolution: Impact on Science and Technology* (1996), pp. 186–189.
- [HRS96] E.R. Hilf, G. Rohen, and T. Severiens. "Electronic Information Management in Physics". In: *Software-Entwicklung in der Chemie* 10 (1996). <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/publications/hilf-1994-4.pdf>, pp. 89–96. <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/documents/UOL-TH03-96-4/cic.ps>.
- [Hil97c] E.R. Hilf. "Elektronische Informationen für die Physik; Grundsätze eines Informationsmanagements". In: *Physikalische Blätter* 53 Nr.4 (1997). gedruckt erschienen in Phys.Bl. 53 (1997) Nr.4, 310–315., pp. 310–315. [\url{http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/documents/UOL-THE03-97-2/phbl/phbl.html}](http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/documents/UOL-THE03-97-2/phbl/phbl.html).
- [Bor+97] Uwe M. Borghoff et al. "Agent-Based Document Retrieval for the European Physicists: A Project Overview". In: *Proceedings of the 2nd Conference on Practical Applications of Intelligent Agents and MultiAgent Technology (PAAM 97)* (1997). <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/documents/UOL-THE03-97-3/paam.ps> and <http://inf2-www.informatik.unibw-muenchen.de/People/borghoff/pspapers/paam97b.ps>, pp. 271 –285.
- [Hil98] Eberhard R. Hilf. "Sammlung Deutscher Quellen zum Copyright/Urheberrecht für Wissenschaftler". In: *Bündnis Urheberrecht für Bildung und Wissenschaft*. auf dem server <http://www.urheberrechtsbuendnis.de/>. 1998. <http://physnet.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/~hilf/IuK/dienste/copyright-de.html>.
- [Hil99b] E.R. Hilf. "Informationsmanagement für die Wissenschaft: Eine Aufgabe der Bibliotheken? (Publikation von Wissenschaft an der Hochschule-Kooperation zwischen Wissenschaftlern und ihrer Bibliothek)". In: lokale Kopie: <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/elib98.htm>, open access: <https://eldorado.tu-dortmund.de/html/2003/2146/elib98.htm>. Nov. 1999. DOI: [\url{http://dx.doi.org/10.17877/DE290R-12758}](http://dx.doi.org/10.17877/DE290R-12758). <http://hdl.handle.net/2003/2146>.
- [Hil99a] Eberhard R. Hilf. "Wie das Internet die Wissenschaft verändert". In: *Bild der Wissenschaft* 5 (1999). Rubrik: Argumente.

- [HSZ99] E.R. Hilf, T. Severiens, and K. Zimmermann. “Distributed Science Online Services by Distributed Workforce”. In: *Future of Mathematical Communication*. This contribution was given and audiorecorded. The record has been, as all the others, dropped by the institution when moving their repositories. Berkeley, USA, Dec. 1, 1999. <http://www.msri.org/publications/ln/msri/1999/fmc99/hilf/1/>.
- [...99] ... “Physik Handbuch: Kapitel 3”. In: *Physik-Handbuch*. 1999.
- [HSH00] Michael Hohlfeld, Thomas Severiens, and Eberhard R. Hilf. “MareNet - ein elektronischer Informationsdienst für die Meeresforschung”. In: *DGM Mitteilungen (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Meeresforschung)* Nr. 3/00 (2000).
- [HSZ00] E. R. Hilf, T. Severiens, and K. Zimmermann. “Wissenschaftliche Kommunikation: Nutzer - MetaData - Management”. In: *Kongress Information und Öffentlichkeit - zugleich 90. Bibliothekartag und 52. Jahrestag der DGI*. Leipzig, Mar. 2000. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/talks/dgi-2000/>.
- [HZ00] E.R. Hilf and K. Zimmermann. “Dissertationen via Internet: Voraussetzungen, Verfahren, Verträge”. In: *Zeitschrift für Bibliothekswesen und Bibliographie. Sonderheft 80* (2000). Band 80 ist bei Klostermann nicht verfügbare, pp. 229 –240.
- [Sev+00] T. Severiens et al. “PhysDoc - A Distributed Network of Physics Institutions Documents: Collecting, Indexing, and Searching High Quality Documents by using Harvest”. In: *D-Lib Magazine* 6 (2000), p. 12. DOI: [doi:10.1045/december2000-severiens](https://doi.org/10.1045/december2000-severiens). <http://www.dlib.org/dlib/december00/severiens/12severiens.html>.
- [ZSH00] Kerstin Zimmermann, Thomas Severiens, and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Ihre Homepage als Beitrag zu einem Fach-Informationsnetz”. In: *Physikalische Blätter* 56.4 (2000). the link to the Publisher version has changed. They serve now http://file:///Users/hilf/Documents/Ihre_Homepage_als_Beitrag_zu... Informatio.pdf, and the online published version of the publisher is of 2013 (sic) <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/phbl.20000560402/epdf> and does not mention the coauthors and does not give the link list. DOI: [DOI:10.1002/phbl.20000560402](https://doi.org/10.1002/phbl.20000560402).
- [Eib+ u] K. Eibl et al. “SCHRIFT UND BILD IN BEWEGUNG”. In: *Fachkongress Elektronisches Publizieren*. Ludwig Maximilians Universität München; Institut für Deutsche Philologie, 27. UND 28. Mai 2000.
- [FZH00] E.A. Fox, R. Zia, and E.R. Hilf. “Open Archives: Distributed services for physicists and graduate students (OAD), NSF IIS-0086227”. In: (2000).

- [HS00] Eberhard R. Hilf and Thomas Severiens. “Experiences and Organisation of the European Physical Society Portal of Services; - Invoking International and National Societies and University Groups Worldwide”. In: *Conference: Lissabon EPS PhysNet 2000*. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/talks/oai2000-hil.html>. 2000. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/talks/oai2000-hil.html>.
- [SH00b] Thomas Severiens and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Using XML for encoding Metadata in distributed systems (PhysDoc)”. In: *Lissabon EPS PhysNet 2000*. 2000. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/talks/oai2000-sev.html>.
- [SH00a] T. Severiens and E. R. Hilf. “Verteilte Strukturen, internationale Einbettung und Arbeitsteilung eines Physik-Portals: Implementierung der Fachbereichsinformationen in ein internationales Physik-Portal”. In: *IuK-Physik 2000 Herbsttagung Bad Honnef*. Presentation. Dec. 2000. http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/talks/2000_BadHonnef/talk1/.
- [Hil+01] Eberhard R. Hilf et al. “Distributed Information Services in Physics”. In: *High Energy Physics Library Webzine 4* (2001). <http://hdl.handle.net/10760/4256>, URI: <http://library.cern.ch/HEPLW/4/papers/2/>. <http://library.web.cern.ch/library/Webzine/4/papers/2/>.
- [E.R01] E.R.Hilf. “Subject specific international services in Physics”. In: ed. by Thomas; Stamerjohanns Heinrich Herausgeber: Bahne Thorsten; Fischer. Duisburg-Ruhrort. University Duisburg - Essen; DuEPublic 5158, 2001. <https://duepublico.uni-duisburg-essen.de/services/DerivateServlet/Derivate-5158/TBand.pdf>.
- [HW01] E.R. Hilf and H.J. Waetjen. “Scientific refereeing in a distributed world and the worldwide physics network physNet”. In: *CERN Series* (2001). Workshop on OAi and Peer Review Journals in Europe; CERN 2001.
- [SH01] T. Severiens and E. R. Hilf. “Fachportal-Physik.de Ideen für ein Physik-Portal”. In: *Meeting of the Physics Portal Group*. Hamburg, Oct. 2001. http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/talks/portal_aki_hh/.
- [Hil01] E. R. Hilf. “Physics Archiving: Requirements, Perspectives, and some Approaches in Germany. in: Session IV: The view of End-user Physicists”. In: *Long Term Archiving of Digital Documents in Physics*. CNRS, Villeurbane, France: IUPAP Conference, <https://journals.aps.org/IUPAP#cpp1>, Nov. 2001. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/lyon01/lyon01-talk.html>.

- [Hil02a] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Electronic Services in the Sciences: international work-sharing, competition, quality control- and the habits of us all*. Ed. by David Goodman. Colloquium. Long Island University, USA, 2002. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/nyc02.html>.
- [HM02c] Eberhard R. Hilf and Julika Mimkes. *Zu einem verlustfreien Publizieren und Archivieren – Mathematische Aussagen in Physik und Chemie; Towards lossless publication - mathematical content in physics and chemistry*. 2002. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/mathdiss02/>.
- [HK02] Eberhard R. Hilf and Thomas Krichel. *42nd Street paper: scholarly communication is author-driven rather than reader-driven*. <http://acis.openlib.org/documents/42st.html>. 2002.
- [Hil02b] E.R. Hilf. “Copyright, Urheberrecht und die Anforderungen der Wissenschaften”. In: (2002). in: DINI zum Copyright <http://physnet.uni-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/dini-copy02/>; Vortrag in: DINI zum Copyright. <http://physnet.uni-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/dini-copy02/>.
- [HM02b] Eberhard R. Hilf and Julika Mimkes. “Metadaten, Nachweis und Nutzung von E-Learning”. In: *Anforderungen durch E-Learning*. DINI Jahrestagung. Dresden, Sept. 2002. <http://www.dini.de/fileadmin/jahrestagungen/2002/vortrag.html>.
- [HM02a] Eberhard R. Hilf and Julika Mimkes. “Learning and Research Success: the role of libraries in the IT age”. In: *High Quality Information For Everyone And What It Costs*. 6th European Bielefeld Colloquium. 2002. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/bielefeld02/talk.html>.
- [HSK02] Eberhard R. Hilf, Roland Schwaenzl, and Michael Kaplan. *abschlussbericht des Teilprojektes Fachübergreifende Informationssysteme; SFM CARMEN; BMBF*. TIB Hannover; Signatur Q1(143,34). 2002.
- [HMS03] Eberhard R. Hilf, Julika Mimkes, and Helmut Schottmüller. *Zu einem verlustfreien Publizieren und Archivieren mathematischer Aussagen in eLearning-Modulen*. Guestrow; Vortrag. 2003. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/guestrow03/guestrow03-scroll.html>.
- [SH03] T. Severiens and E. R. Hilf. *Aufbau eines Systems für die Erschließung verteilter Dokumente in der Internationalen Pädagogischen Forschung*. Talk. Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg, 2003. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/talks/sub-hh.pdf>.

- [Hil04a] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Conference Report on the IUPAP Workshop on Scientific Misconduct and the role of Physics Journals in its Investigation and Prevention*. Oldenburg, 2004. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/london03/report2EPS.pdf>.
- [Har+04b] Stevan Harnad et al. “The Access/Impact Problem and the Green and Gold Roads to Open Access”. In: *Serials review* 30.4 (2004), pp. 310–314. <http://www.citebase.org/cgi-bin/citations?id=oai:eprints.ecs.soton.ac.uk:9939>.
- [Har+04a] S. Harnad et al. “The green and the gold roads to Open Access”. In: *Nature* 17; Web focus on access to literature (2004). <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/259940/>.
- [SHtb] H. Stamerjohanns and E. R. Hilf. “Wie wird meine Publikation häufiger zitiert? Literatur online zu präsentieren hat viele Vorteile”. In: *UNI-INFO Oldenburg* 31. Jahrgang 7 (Oktber 2004). <http://www.uni-oldenburg.de/presse/uni-info/2004/7/forschung.htm>.
- [Poyv] Richard Poynder. *No Gain without Pain*. Interview with Eberhard R. Hilf and others; summary on Open Access development and Publishers. Nov. 2004.
- [SMH04] Michael Schlenker, Julika Mimkes, and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Dynamic Thesaurus and Dynamic Discovery of Distributed eLearning Materials”. In: *IT Innovation in a Changing World*. EUNIS. Presentation:<http://www.authorstream.com/Presentation/Rosalie-31851-eunis-vortrag2004-Dynamic-Thesaurus-Discovery-DistributedeLearning-Materials-Institute-Science-Networking-as-Entertainment-ppt-powerpoint/>. Bled, Slovenia, 2004. <http://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/docs/00/03/41/08/PDF/eunis2004.pdf>.
- [Hil04b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Zehn Jahre Open Access - und nun die wirtschaftliche Nutzung?” In: *Medien Wirtschaft* 3 (2004). ISSN: 1613-0669.
- [HS04] E. R. Hilf and T. Severiens. *Vernetzung offener, verteilter Portale*. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/aki04/dpg-muenchen-2004.pdf>. München, 2004. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/publications/aki-muenchen-2004.pdf>.
- [SH04] Thomas Severiens and Eberhard Hilf. *Elf Argumente fuer Open Access*. Institute for Science Networking Oldenburg, Germany. 2004. <http://old.isn-oldenburg.de/publications/11argumente.html>.
- [Hil m] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Kann man TeX beibringen, Physik zu verstehen?* 10. Mai 2005. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/texdocc05/>.

- [Hil05b] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Document Retrieval System DoRe für das Großforschungsinstitut GSI Darmstadt*. http://www.gsi.de/search/DoRe/index_e.html. . 2005. <http://www.gsi.de/harvest/graphics/index.html>.
- [HSS05] Eberhard R. Hilf, Thomas Severiens, and Michael Schlenker. “Towards a Physics Markup Language”. In: *MKM Mathematical Knowledge Management; Sesame 2005 Workshop Bremen*. <http://www.mkm-ig.org/meetings/sesame05/>. 2005. <http://www.isn-oldeenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/sesame05/sesame-0.html>.
- [RGH05] Hans E. Roosendaal, Peter A. Th. M. Geurts, and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Pertinent Strategy Issues in Scientific Information and Communication in 2004”. In: *Library Science- quo vadis? editor: Petra Hauke*. Invited review. Institute of Library Science at the Humboldt University Berlin: K.G. Saur Verlag, München, 2005, pp. 217–238.
- [Hil06a] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Bibliometrics of science impact of scientists and of papers*. Blog: zugang-zum-wissen-journal 4.Oct.2006. 2006. <http://www.zugang-zum-wissen.de/journal/index.php?archiv es/11-Bibliometrics-of-science-impact-of-scientists-and-of-papers.html>.
- [Hil06b] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Erschließung von Zitationen in verteilten Repositorien; Distributed Open Access Citation Services DOARC; Ein Teildienst des Netzwerk zertifizierter Open-Access-Repositories*. Report auf dem DINI-Vorbereitungstreffen, Berlin. 2006. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/berlin06/slot3-0.html>.
- [HKS06] Eberhard R. Hilf, Michael Kohlhase, and Heinrich Stamerjohanns. “Capturing the Content of Physics: Systems, Observables, and Experiments”. In: *Mathematical Knowledge Management, MKM’06; number 4108 in LNAI*. Ed. by Jon Borwein and William M. Farmer. LNAI Lecture Notes in Computer Science 4108. doi:10.1007/11812289_14, and. Springer Verlag, 2006, pp. 165–178. <http://www.isn-oldeenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/mkm06-paper.pdf>.
- [Dob+06] Susanne Dobratz et al. *National Open Access Portal NOAP. Arbeitspapier für die DINI-Arbeitsgruppe Elektronische Publikationen*. 2006. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/dini06-sketch.pdf>.
- [HS06] Eberhard R. Hilf and Michael Schlenker. *Web-search of Physics Content- The Concept of Physics Markup Language*. Hauptvortrag; http://www.aki-dpg.de/aki_prog_2006.pdf. 2006.

- [Hil82] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Open Access wird Ihnen die Arbeit erleichtern.* siehe auch: V.Renkes, E-Journale bringen Schwung in die Wissenschaft, DUZ Magazin: Werkstatt, 8,p.2 (2006), <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/DUZ-WerkstattE-Journals2-3.pdf>. 25.8.2008. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/DUZ-Open-accessS8-9.pdf>.
- [SHbr] Thomas Severiens and Eberhard R. Hilf. *Zur Entwicklung eines Beschreibungsprofils für eine nationale Langzeit-Archivierungs-Strategie (National Long-term Preservation Policy) - ein Beitrag aus der Sicht der Wissenschaften.* Februar 2006. [\url{http://edoc.hu-berlin.de/docviews/abstract.php?id=26669}](http://edoc.hu-berlin.de/docviews/abstract.php?id=26669).
- [Har+06] Stevan Harnad et al. *Open Access Scientometrics.* <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/euroscience-metrics.pdf> and <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/pub-hilf/2006/8/euroscience-metrics.pdf>. Draft for a sketch for an EU-Proposal of a joint project of University Southampton, UK; CNRS, FR; University Minho, PT; DINI, DE; 2006.
- [SH] Thomas Severiens and Eberhard R. Hilf. *Langzeitarchivierung von Rohdaten.* URN: urn:nbn:de:0008-20051114018. [\url{http://edoc.hu-berlin.de/docviews/abstract.php?id=27025}](http://edoc.hu-berlin.de/docviews/abstract.php?id=27025).
- [Hil07] Eberhard R. Hilf. "Digitaler Open Access zu wissenschaftlichen Informationen - Ein Umbruch zu neuen professionellen Diensten". In: *Open Source Jahrbuch 2007 - Zwischen freier Software und Gesellschaftsmodell.* Ed. by Bernd Lutterbeck, Matthias Bärwolff, and Robert A. Gehring. Artikel als 'unter den top ten aller OS Jahrbuchartikel' bewertet. Berlin: Lehmanns Media, 2007.
- [BHR07] Knut Barghorn, Eberhard R. Hilf, and Hans E. Roosendaal. *White paper on scientific publishing.* Scine; Consulting and Management of scientific information. 2007. <http://www.scine-all.de/materials/whitepaper.pdf>.
- [Hilde] Eberhard R. Hilf. *..und wie können Autoren ihre Publikationen Open Access stellen?* Zugang zum Wissen; Blog. 10.Dec. 2007. <http://www.zugang-zum-wissen.de/journal/index.php?/archives/25-..und-wie-koennen-Autoren-ihre-Publikationen-Open-Access-stellen.html>.
- [Hilec] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Neues Urheberrecht: Wahrung von Rechten der Autoren an eigenen Publikationen.* Zugang zum Wissen; Blog. 7.Dec. 2007. <http://www.zugang-zum-wissen.de/journal/index.php?/archives/24-Neues-Urheberrecht-Wahrung-von-Rechten-der-Autoren-an-eigenen-Publikationen.html>.

- [Aig+07] Ph. Aigrain et al. *Suggestions for optimising the European Commission's Recommendation to mandate open access Archiving of Publicly-funded research*. a copy at ISN: <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/pub-hilf/euroscience-oa-suggestions-to-EU-2007.pdf>. <http://www.scientificcommons.org/42571822>, 2007. http://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/euroscience.pdf.
- [Har+08] Stevan Harnad et al. "The Access/Impact Problem and the Green and Gold Roads to Open Access: An Update". In: *Serials Review* 34.1 (Mar. 2008). url = <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/265852/>, pp. 36–40. ISSN: 0098-7913. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.serrev.2007.12.005> doi:10.1016/j.serrev.2007.12.005. <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/265852/1/serev-revised.pdf>.
- [Chr+ne] Wolfgang Christen et al. *Erschliessung von Zitationen in verteilten Open-Access-Repositoryen (Distributed Open Access Reference Citation Services) DOARC*. <http://eve.mathematik.uni-osnabrueck.de/wiki/images/8/87/Slot3-Antrag-2-final-public-3.pdf>. Konzeption des Antrages an die Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft DFG; Teilprojekt zum *Open Access Network* von DINI Deutsche Initiative für NetzwerkInformation, see <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/pub-hilf/documents/2008/2/Slot3-Antrag-2-final-public-3.pdf>. June 2008.
- [HKR08] Eberhard R. Hilf, B. Kappenberg, and Hans E. Roosendaal. "Author identification: The benefit of being able to identify researchers uniquely". In: *The Euroscientist* 5 (Dec. 2008). Ed. by Alma Swan. <https://web.archive.org/web/20110930183555/http://www.euroscience.org/author-identification,28115,en.html>.
- [Hilno] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Helene Bosc über den Erfolg zentraler vs. verteilter Open Access Repositoryen*. Zugang zum Wissen; Blog. 25.Nov.2008. <http://www.zugang-zum-wissen.de/journal/index.php?/permalink/Helene-Bosc-ueber-den-Erfolg-zentraler-vs.-verteilter-Open-Access-Repositoryen.html>.
- [Hilma] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Cochrane Library Bezahlmodell von STM-Zeitschriften*. Zugang zum Wissen; Blog. 14.March 2008. <http://www.zugang-zum-wissen.de/journal/index.php?/archives/36-Cochrane-Library-Bezahlmodell-von-STM-Zeitschriften.html>.
- [Hilja] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Open Access: Jura, Rechtswissenschaften*. 24.Jan. 2008. <http://www.zugang-zum-wissen.de/journal/index.php?/archives/26-Open-Access-Jura,-Rechtswissenschaften.html>.
- [Hil08] Eberhard R. Hilf. "Fünfzehn Jahre Open Access wissenschaftlicher Ergebnisse". In: *Archivalia; Blog*. Ed. by Klaus Graf. ein Beitrag zum Tag des Open Access 2008. Oct. 2008.

- [Mö9b] Christine Xuan Müller. “Digital Author Identifier: Die Forscher-ID kann Namensprobleme lösen und die Karriere befördern”. In: *duz Europa kompakt* 02 (2009). der Artikel basiert auf einem Telefon-Interview mit Eberhard R. Hilf, p. 7.
- [Hil09i] Eberhard R. Hilf. *zur Geschichte von Open Access in den Naturwissenschaften und in der Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg*. Ed. by Institute for Science Networking Oldenburg GmbH. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/oops2009.pdf>. Kurzfilm. 2009. <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vHmP8eAJMak>.
- [Poy09b] Richard Poynder. *Open Access: Profile of Eberhard Hilf*. 2009. http://www.richardpoynder.co.uk/Hilf_Interview.pdf.
- [Roo+10] Hans E. Roosendaal et al. *Scientific Publishing: from Vanity to Strategy*. mit einem online Open Access Summary. Woodhead Publishing Limited, Jan. 2010. DOI: [doi:10.1016/B978-1-84334-490-2.50009-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-84334-490-2.50009-8).
- [PH10] Richard Poynder and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Interview on Open Access in Germany”. In: *Blog: Open and Shut?* 2010. [/url{http://www.poynder.blog.com}](http://www.poynder.blog.com).
- [Mau10] Michael Maune. *Distributed Open Access Reference Citations Service DOARC*. Aalborg, Denmark, 2010. http://www.eurocris.org/Uploads/Web_pages/cris2010_papers/PPT/cris2010_Maune.ppt.
- [Mau+10] Michael Maune et al. “Distributed Open Access Reference Citations Service DOARC”. In: *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Current Research Information Systems (euroCRIS 2010): Connecting Science with Society The Role of Research Information in a Knowledge-Based Society*. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/projects/doarc2/veroeffentlichungen/Cris2010.pdf>. Aalborg, Denmark, 2010. http://www.eurocris.org/Uploads/Web_pages/cris2010_papers/Papers/cris2010_Maune.pdf.
- [HS13] Eberhard R. Hilf and Thomas Severiens. “Vom Open Access für Dokumente und Daten zu Open Content in der Wissenschaft”. In: *Grundlagen der praktischen Information und Dokumentation*. Ed. by Dietmar Strauch Rainer Kuhlen Wolfgang Semar. Vol. 6. Ausgabe. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/uploads/publications/2013/oa-doc-and-content.pdf>. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2013, pp. 379–395. ISBN: ISBN:978-3-11-025822-6. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/en/research/publications/2013/vom-open-access-fuer-dokumente-und-daten-zu-open/>.
- [SH14] Thomas Severiens and Eberhard R. Hilf. In: Springer VS, 2014. Chap. A scientific editor’s support tool: design, analysis and value, S.5 bis S.30. <http://www.eerqi.eu/>.

- [Hil17] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Was wissen Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftler über ihre Urheberrechte, wie handeln sie, und was wünschen sie? Umfrage zum Urheberrechtsgesetz an wissenschaftlichen Hochschulen”. In: *Aktionsbündnis Urheberrecht für Bildung und Wissenschaft; Server: Veröffentlichungen* (2017). <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/urhg-umfrage-Teil-1-3-public.pdf>.
- [Hil18] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Zur Zukunft des Aktionsbündnis Urheberrecht für Bildung und Wissenschaft*. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/ab-hilfs-thesen.pdf>. 2018.

3 Theoretical Physics of atomic clusters

3.1 Theoretical Physics of atomic Clusters

- [DH74] P K Draxl and E R Hilf. “Quadratsummen und gewisse Randwertprobleme der mathematischen Physik”. In: *J. Reine Angew. Math.*, (1974).
- [BHP74a] H. P. Baltes, E. R. Hilf, and M. Pabst. “Erratum”. In: *Applied Physics* 5 (Oct. 1974), pp. 83–83. DOI: [10.1007/BF01193403](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01193403).
- [Hild] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Zur Theoretischen Physik der Bildung und der thermodynamischen Eigenschaften kleiner Systeme”. In: *Erstes Kolloquium im DFG-Schwerpunktprogramm Physik anorganischer Cluster*. Vortrag. Bad Honnef 1985.
- [Hil87] E. R. Hilf. “Cluster physics - some remarks”. In: *PDMS and Clusters*. Ed. by Eberhard R. Hilf AND F. Kammer AND K. Wien. Vol. 269. Lecture Notes in Physics, Berlin Springer Verlag. Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on the Physics of Small Systems; Held on the Island of Wangerooge, Germany September 8–12, 1986. 1987, pp. 251–257. DOI: [10.1007/3-540-17209-2_60](https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-17209-2_60).
- [GRP88] G.Franke, Eberhard R.Hilf, and L. Polley. “Quantum-Mechanics and Phase Transitions in small noble-gas clusters”. In: *Zeitschrift für Physik D 9, Atoms, Molecules and Clusters* (1988). DOI: [10.1007/BF01436942](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01436942). eprint: [PreprintU0-Phys-TH-87-09; August1987](http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THE03/publications/quantum.mechanics.prep.pdf). <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THE03/publications/quantum.mechanics.prep.pdf>.
- [FHB93] Gert Franke, Eberhard R. Hilf, and Peter Borrmann. “The structure of small clusters: Multiple normal-modes model”. In: *J.Chem.Phys.* 98 (1993). DOI: [10.1063/1.464070](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.464070). http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THE03/publications/borrmann_diss.pdf#page=96.
- [BH93] P. Borrmann and E. R. Hilf. “Structure and stability of polarized Li(3)-He(N)+ cluster ions”. In: *Zeitschrift für Physik D Atoms Molecules Clusters D 26* (Mar. 1993), pp. 350–352. DOI: [10.1007/BF01425713](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01425713).

- [BH94] Peter Borrmann and Eberhard R. Hilf. “New enhancements to Feynmans Path Integral for fermions”. In: *ArXiv:cond-mat/9412113* <http://arxiv.org/abs/cond-mat/9412113v1> (1994).
- [Hil94b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Foreword”. In: vol. 2. Proceedings of the International Workshop on Theory of Atomic and Molecular Clusters, Leer (Ostfriesland), Germany, June 1993. 1994. DOI: [doi:10.1016/0927-0256\(94\)90065-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-0256(94)90065-5). http://www.sciencedirect.com/science?_ob=ArticleURL&_udi=B6TWM-48FKDGT-3N&_user=10&_coverDate=07%2F31%2F1994&_rdoc=1&_fmt=summary&_orig=browse&_sort=d&view=c&_acct=C000050221&_version=1&_urlVersion=0&_userid=10&md5=75be04465f445ece6cf2030f380b15ed.
- [Bor+94] P. Borrmann et al. “Magnetism of small transition metal clusters and the effects of isomerisation”. In: *arXiv:cond-mat/9412121* (1994). <http://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/9412121v1>.
- [BGH94a] P. Borrmann, D. Gloski, and E.R. Hilf. “Specific heat in the thermodynamics of clusters”. In: *ArXiv: http://arxiv.org/abs/chem-ph/9412003* (1994).
- [DBH94] B. Diekmann, P. Borrmann, and E.R. Hilf. “Structures and Stabilities of H₃+(H₂)_n Clusters (n=1-11)”. In: (1994). DOI: [10.1142/S0218625X96000498](https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218625X96000498).
- [Bor+96a] P. Borrmann et al. “Magnetism of Small Transition-Metal Clusters and Effects of Isomerization”. In: *Surface Review and Letters* 3 (1996), pp. 463–466. DOI: [10.1142/S0218625X96000838](https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218625X96000838).
- [PDE96] Borrmann P., Gloski D., and Hilf E.R. “Specific heat in the thermodynamics of clusters”. In: *Surface Review and Letters* 3.1 (1996), pp. 103–108. DOI: [DOI:10.1142/S0218625X9600022X](https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218625X9600022X).
- [DBH96] B. Diekmann, P. Borrmann, and E. R. Hilf. “Structures and Stabilities of H₃+ H₂(n) Clusters (n=1-11)”. In: *Surface Review and Letters* 3 (1996), pp. 253–257. DOI: [10.1142/S0218625X96000498](https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218625X96000498). eprint: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/9412123.pdf>.
- [Tom+96] D. Tománek et al. “Self-Assembly of Magnetic Nanostructures.” In: *APS March Meeting Abstracts* (Mar. 1996), p. 2201.
- [Bor+96b] P. Borrmann et al. “Thermodynamics of Finite Magnetic Two-Level Systems.” In: *APS March Meeting Abstracts* (Mar. 1996), p. L3326.
- [Tom+97] David Tomanek et al. “Self-assembly of magnetic nanostructures”. In: *Z. Phys. D* 40, Atoms, Molecules and Clusters, Issue 1-4 (1997). <http://www.pa.msu.edu/cmp/csc/eprint/DT090.pdf>, and author-copy: <http://www.pa.msu.edu/cmp/csc/eprint/samagcluster/samagcluster.pdf>. DOI: [10.1007/s004600050272](https://doi.org/10.1007/s004600050272). https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Heinrich_Stamerj

ohanns/publication/34444722_Phase_transitions_in_magnetic_clusters_and_other_finite_systems_Elektronische_Ressource/links/0c96051cdb6242b5fc000000/Phase-transitions-in-magnetic-clusters-and-other-finite-systems-Elektronische-Ressource.pdf#page=52.

- [Hei+97a] H. Heinze et al. “Temperature measurement from scattering spectra of clusters: theoretical treatment”. In: *Z.Phys. D* 40 (1997). DOI: [10.1007/s004600050191](https://doi.org/10.1007/s004600050191). <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.128.2273&rep=rep1&type=pdf#page=43>.
- [Bor+99c] Peter Borrmann et al. “Thermodynamics of finite magnetic two-isomer systems”. In: *Journal of Chemical Physics* 111, 23 (1999). an open access version by the publisher is not available. DOI: [10.1063/1.480423](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.480423).
- [Bor+99b] Peter Borrmann et al. “Calculation of thermodynamic properties of finite Bose-Einstein systems”. In: *Physical Review A* 60(2) (1999). DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevA.60.1519](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.60.1519). eprint: [arXiv:cond-mat/0008071](https://arxiv.org/abs/cond-mat/0008071). <http://alexandria.tue.nl/openaccess/Metis238356.pdf>.
- [Bor+99a] P. Borrmann et al. “Effective calculation of thermodynamic properties of finite Bose-Einstein systems”. In: *Physical Review A* 59.3 (1999).
- [Bor+01] Peter Borrmann et al. “Paradoxical Magnetic Cooling in a Structural Transition Model”. In: *European Physical Journal B* 19 (2001). DOI: [10.1007/s100510170356](https://doi.org/10.1007/s100510170356). eprint: [ArXiv:cond-mat/0009048](https://arxiv.org/abs/cond-mat/0009048) [\url{http://xxx.lanl.gov/abs/cond-mat/0009048}](http://xxx.lanl.gov/abs/cond-mat/0009048) and [MSUPreprint\url{http://www.pa.msu.edu/cmp/csc/eprint/DT097.pdf}](http://www.pa.msu.edu/cmp/csc/eprint/DT097.pdf).

4 Thermodynamics

4.1 Thermodynamics

- [Hil66] E.R. Hilf. *Oberflächenpannung und Thermodynamik des Idealen Gases*. Dissertation, University of Frankfurt a. Main, Germany. 1966.
- [Hil67b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Oberflächenspannung und Thermodynamik perfekter Gase”. In: (1967). BASE: <http://www.base-search.net/Search/Results?lookfor=Hilf&type=aut&lem=0&lem=1&gs=0&thes=0&refid=dcreesen&newressearch=1>. <http://publikationen.ub.uni-frankfurt.de/volltexte/2009/7200/>.
- [Hild] Eberhard R. Hilf. *die Thermodynamischen Begriffe*. Ed. by herausgegeben von den Fachredaktionen des Bibliographischen Instituts Redaktionelle Leitung: Johannes Kunsemüller.

- [Hil69b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Oberflächen- und Krümmungsspannung idealer Gase”. In: *Frühjahrstagung der Deutschen Physikalischen Gesellschaft DPG*. Ed. by Fachausschuss Thermodynamik. München. 1969.
- [EH69] Rolf Ebert and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Weyl Problem ad surface effects of ideal quantummechanical gases”. In: *Journ. of the Phys. Soc. of Japan*. Vol. 26, Suppl. Proceedings of the Int. Conf. on Statistical Mechanics; Kyoto, Japan 1968. 1969.
- [Hil70b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Oberflächenspannung und Thermodynamik des perfekten Gases”. In: *Zeitschrift Naturforschung Teil A Band 25a, Heft 8/9 (1970)*. Original (Papier): Universitaet Frankfurt a.Main; <https://lbsopac.rz.uni-frankfurt.de/DB=30/SET=10/TTL=2/SHW?FRST=1>.
- [SH70] G. Süßmann and E. R. Hilf. “General Definition of the Perfect Gas Concept”. In: *Pure and Applied Chemistry; The official Journal of the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry* 22 (1970). International Conference on Thermodynamics. <https://www.iupac.org/publications/pac/pdf/1970/pdf/2203x0243.pdf>.
- [Hil70a] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Die perfekten Gase”. In: *Tagung der Deutschen Physikalischen Gesellschaft DPG*. Ed. by Fachausschuss Thermodynamik. Vol. Freudenstadt. Review-Vortrag. 1970.
- [BH70] Wolfgang Bauer and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Equation of State of the Perfect Fermi-Gas”. In: *Phys. Lett.* 32, No.3 (1970). DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-9601\(70\)90268-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-9601(70)90268-9).
- [Bau+70] W. Bauer et al. “The Perfect Gases”. In: *Astronomy and Astrophysics* (1970). accepted.
- [HSri] Eberhard R. Hilf and Georg Süßmann. “Simplified Notation of Partial Derivatives for use in Thermodynamics”. In: nicht vorgetragen, da Reiseantrag nicht genehmigt. April 1971.
- [BH72] H. P. Baltes and E. R. Hilf. “Progress in Weyl’s problem achieved by computational methods”. In: *Computer Physics Communications* 4.2 (1972). The Impact of Computers on Physics, pp. 208 – 213. ISSN: 0010-4655. DOI: [DOI:10.1016/0010-4655\(72\)90010-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-4655(72)90010-0). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TJ5-46DF8SN-1M/2/6f972eb342e3838c7e06b47a4ce3d237>.
- [Bau+74] W. D. Bauer et al. *The Perfect Gases; A Review*. Ed. by Benjamin Gal Or. Preprint IKDA 73-13 (Institut fuer Kernphysik TH Darmstadt preprint series). Wiley and Sons, 1974. <http://smallsystems.isn-oldenburg.de/publications/metadocs/ebs.PerfQuantGas.html>.

- [HE73] H.P.Baltes and E.R.Hilf. "Specific heat of lead grains". In: *Solid State Communications* 12.5 (1973). Das nicht-quadratische Verhalten des Überschusses $DC = C - C_{\text{bulk}}$ der spezifischen Wärme, wie er unterhalb von 5K von Novotny, Meincke und Watson an Bleipartikeln mit 22 Angstrom Durchmesser beobachtet wurde, wird durch exakte Summation aller Vibrationszustände der entsprechenden freien Kugel im Rahmen eines Kontinuumsmodells erklärt. Darüberhinaus wird ein Maximum des Überschusses bei etwa 8K vorausgesagt. Die mittlere quadratische Frequenz ω quadrat wird berechnet., pp. 369 –373. ISSN: 0038-1098. DOI: [DOI : 10 . 1016 / 0038 - 1098 \(73\) 90775 - 8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1098(73)90775-8). eprint: [ePrintNovember1972 : Institut f \ "ur Kernphysik , THDarmstadt , Germany . http : // www . sciencedirect . com / science / article / B6TVW - 46TYS1X - WN / 2 / 5d1daf14d1eb5ce2baf7e497b28f0af](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TVW-46TYS1X-WN/2/5d1daf14d1eb5ce2baf7e497b28f0af).
- [BHP74b] H.P. Baltes, E.R. Hilf, and M. Pabst. "The Long-Time Behaviour of the Electric Field Autocorrelation Function in a Finite Photon Gas". In: *Appl.Phys.* 3 (1974). DOI: [10 . 1007 / BF00892330](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00892330).
- [BH76] H.P. Baltes and E.R. Hilf. "Spectra of finite systems. A review of Weyl's problem, the eigenvalue distribution of the wave equation for finite domains and its applications on the physics of small systems". In: (1976). Full text Open Access Online. [https : // scholar . google . de / scholar ? oi = bibs \ & hl = de \ & cluster = 6085681317357528666 \ & btnl = Lucky](https://scholar.google.de/scholar?oi=bibs&hl=de&cluster=6085681317357528666&btnl=Lucky).
- [Chagu] John L. Challifour. "H.P.Baltes and Eberhard R. Hilf: Spectra of Finite Systems". In: *Physics today* 30(8) (August 1, 1977). Buchbesprechung. DOI: [http : // dx . doi . org / 10 . 1063 / 1 . 3037672](http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.3037672).
- [BHC77] H. P. Baltes, E. R. Hilf, and J. L. Challifour. "Spectra of Finite Systems". In: *Physics Today* 30 (1977), p. 55. DOI: [10 . 1063 / 1 . 3037672](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3037672).
- [BGH94b] Peter Borrmann, Dorian Gloski, and Eberhard R Hilf. "Specific heat in the thermodynamics of clusters". In: (1994). [http : // arxiv . org / pdf / chem - ph / 9412003v1](http://arxiv.org/pdf/chem-ph/9412003v1).
- [Bor+96] Peter Borrmann et al. "Thermodynamics of finite magnetic two-level systems". In: *eprint arXiv:cond-mat/9601138* (1996). [http : // arxiv . org / abs / cond - mat / 9601138v1](http://arxiv.org/abs/cond-mat/9601138v1).
- [Hei+97b] H. Heinze et al. "Temperature measurement from scattering spectra of clusters: theoretical treatment". In: *Zeitschrift f. Physik D* 40 (1997). [http : // citeseerx . ist . psu . edu / viewdoc / download ? doi = 10 . 1 . 1 . 128 . 2273 & rep = rep1 & type = pdf # page = 48](http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.128.2273&rep=rep1&type=pdf#page=48).
- [BH99] P. Borrmann and E.R. Hilf. *Statistische Physik*. Vorlesung. 1999.

5 Quantum Physics

5.1 Quantum Physics

- [HP81] Eberhard R. Hilf and Lutz Polley. “Stability and Screening solutions in a semi-classical Yang-Mills Theory proposed by Pagels and Tomboulis”. In: *Institut für Kernphysik, TH Darmstadt, Germany IKDA 81/8* (1981).
- [PH82] Lutz Polley and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Bag formation in effective Yang-Mills theory”. In: *IOP Conference on Nuclear Structure and Particle Physics*. preprint 2nd edition: 1983. 1982. eprint: <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THE03/publications/bs.bag.formation.pdf>.
- [HP84b] Eberhard R. Hilf and Lutz Polley. “Effective QCD-Lagrangian for Nuclear Physics”. In: vol. 197. *Lecture Notes in Physics*. Preprint IKDA 83/26 Institute for Nuclear Physics, TH Darmstadt, Germany. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1984. Chap. Chapter 4. Quark Structure of Nuclei. ISBN: 978-3-540-12922-6. DOI: [doi:10.1007/3-540-12922-7_191](https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-12922-7_191). eprint: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227314103_Effective_QCD-Lagrangian_for_nuclear_physics.
- [Kle+86] Burkhard Kleihaus et al. “Wilson Action in terms of the Kogut-Susskind Fermion Matrix”. In: *Preprint-Series of Theory Group III, Department of Physics, University Oldenburg, Germany UO-PHYS-THEO-06, May 1986* UO-PHYS-THEO-06 (1986). PACS96: 11.15.Ha Lattice gauge theory PACS96: 02.70.+d Computational methods.

6 Mathematics

6.1 Mathematics

- [Hil64] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Greensche Operatoren in der Ortsdarstellung und Hartree-Fock-Näherung*. Vortrag am Institut für Theoretische Physik, Universität Frankfurt a.Main, Germany. 1964.
- [DH74] P K Draxl and E R Hilf. “Quadratsummen und gewisse Randwertprobleme der mathematischen Physik”. In: *J. Reine Angew. Math*, (1974).

7 Physics of PDMS Plasma Desorption Mass Spectrometry

7.1 The Physics of PDMS Plasma Desorption Mass Spectrometry

- [Cur93] Beate Curdes. *Molekuel-Bildungsprozesse bei der Plasma-Desorptions-Massenspektrometrie PDMS*. Diplomarbeit at University Oldenburg, Germany. 1993. eprint: http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THE03/publications/bcurdes_dipl.pdf.
- [ERH86] Karl Wien Eberhard R. Hilf Fritz Kammer, ed. *PDMS and Clusters*. Vol. 269. Lecture Notes in Physics. Springer, 1986. DOI: [10.1007/3-540-17209-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-17209-2).
- [KH86] H.F. Kammer and Eberhard. R. Hilf. "Excitation of lattice motion by interaction with large amplitude electron plasma oscillations". In: *Solid State Communications* 58.7 (1986), pp. 465–468. ISSN: 0038-1098. DOI: [DOI : 10.1016/0038-1098\(86\)90033-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1098(86)90033-5). <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/documents/UOL-THE03-85-3/85-3.pdf>.
- [HKW87] Eberhard R. Hilf, F. Kammer, and K. Wien. "PDMS and Clusters". In: *Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on the Physics of Small Systems; Island of Wangerooge, Germany, September 8–12, 1986*. Ed. by Karl Wien Eberhard R. Hilf Friedrich Kammer. Vol. 269. Lecture Notes in Physics. VCH-Wiley, 1987. DOI: [10.1007/3-540-17209-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-17209-2). <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/3-540-17209-2>.
- [Hil+88] E.R. Hilf et al. "Lassen sich schwere organische Moleküle im Watt wiegen?" In: *Einblicke - Forschungsmagazin der C.v.O.-Universität Oldenburg* Heft 7 (1988).
- [E.R88] H.F.Kammer E.R.Hilf. "Model calculation of Plasma Desorption of Organics". In: *11th International Mass Spectrometry Conference*. Ed. by Hoppilliard et al. Bordeaux, 29.8.-2.9.1988. 1988.
- [TH89] Wilfried Tuszynski and Eberhard R. Hilf. "Massenspektrometrie von Meeresproben - Analyse von Biomolekülen für die Ökosystemforschung". In: *Symposium Nordseeforschung als Beitrag zum Schutz der Nordsee, Bremerhaven*. Plasma- Desorptions- Massenspektrometrie - ein Verfahren der Massenanalyse großer, nichtflüchtiger Moleküle. Vogel Verlag und Druck KG, Würzburg, 1989.
- [Hil+89] E.R. Hilf et al. "HIID of Organics - Calculations and Chlorophyll-a Measurements". In: ed. by P. Longevialle. Vol. 11A. Heyden and Sons Ltd, London, 1989.

- [HK89] E.R. Hilf and H.F. Kammer. “Computer simulation of the HIID from Langmuir-Blodgett films”. English. In: vol. 50. C2. HAL - CCSD : CCSD (Centre pour la Communication Scientifique Directe): HAL - Hyper Article on Line, 1989, pp. C2-245–C2-249. DOI: [10.1051/jphyscol:1989239](https://doi.org/10.1051/jphyscol:1989239). <http://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/jpa-00229438>.
- [HKN89] E. R. Hilf, H. F. Kammer, and B. Nitzschmann. “Status of the Theory of MeV-Ion Electronic Stopping Induced Desorption”. In: *Radiation Effects and Defects in Solids* Vol. 110 (1989). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10420158908214168>.
- [HT90] Eberhard R. Hilf and Wilfried Tuszynski, eds. *Mass Spectrometry of Large Non-Volatile Molecules for Marine Organic Chemistry*. World Scientific, Singapore, 1989, 1990, p. 231. ISBN: ISBN 981-02-0250-4,9789810202507; eISBN: 9789814390170.
- [Hil90] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Preface”. In: *Mass Spectrometry of Large Non-Volatile Molecules for Marine Organic Chemistry*. 1990. http://ebooks.worldscinet.com/ISBN/9789814390170/9789814390170_fmatter.html.
- [EH90] W. Tuszynski und E.R. Hilf. “Massenspektrometrie von Meeresproben - Analyse von Biomolekülen für die Ökosystemforschung”. In: *NATO Advanced Research Workshop on Methods and Mechanisms for Producing Ions from Large Molecules, Minaki, Canada*. 1990.
- [TH90] Wilfried Tuszynski and Eberhard R. Hilf. *High-molecular mass spectroscopy for the wadden sea: Construction and test of a PDMS-facility. (Final report)*. Final Report of BMBF-Project; Identifier: DE_1993:2669;DE; Copy by TIB Technische Informationsbibliothek Hannover FR 6776; <http://edok01.tib.uni-hannover.de/edoks/e01fbdig06/512483574.pdf>. 1990. <http://opac.tib.uni-hannover.de/DB=1/SET=12/TTL=11/SHW?FRST=18>.
- [Har+90] St. Harsdorf et al. “Computer Simulations, Analysis and Transfer of PDMS-Spectra”. In: *Mass Spectrometry of large non-volatile molecules for marine organic chemistry*. Ed. by W. Tuszynski und E.R. Hilf. 1990. ISBN: eISBN: 9789814390170. http://ebooks.worldscinet.com/ISBN/9789814390170/9789814390170_0015.html.
- [KH90] H. F. Kammer and E.R. Hilf. “Excitonic processes in FHIID”. In: *Ion Formation from Organic Solids (IFOS V; 1989)*. Ed. by A. Benninghoven A. Hedin B.U.R.Sundquist. J.Wiley, Chichester, 1990.
- [Hil+91] E.R. Hilf et al. “Chemometry of Plasma Desorption Mass Spectrometry”. In: ed. by J. Gmehling. *Software Development in Chemistry 5*. Springer, Berlin Heidelberg, 1991. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-642-76325-0_15](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-76325-0_15).

- [TH91] W. Tuszynski and E.R. Hilf. "PDMS zur Analyse von Pigmentproben". In: *24. Diskussionstagung der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Massenspektrometrie, Dortmund*. 1991.
- [HK91] E. R. Hilf and H. F. Kammer. "Ion Formation in Electronic Sputtering from Decane". In: *Methods and Mechanisms for Producing Ions from Large Molecules*. Vol. Physics Vol. 269. NATO ASI Series B. Proceedings of a NATO Advanced Research Workshop on Methods and Mechanisms for Producing Ions from Large Molecules, Minaki Lodge, Minaki, Canada, 24-28 June 1990. 1991.
- [Cur+92a] J. Curdes et al. "Analysis of Entropic vs. Thermal Fragmentation". In: *6th Texas Symposium on Mass Spectrometry, Gaspe, Quebec, Canada*. Ed. by R. Macfarlane. 1992.
- [NBH92] B. Nitzschmann, K. Barghorn, and E. R. Hilf. "Simulation of the Desorption Process induced by Fast Ionic Atoms, Molecules or Clusters". In: *The 40th ASMS Conference on Mass Spectrometry and Allied Topics, Washington, DC*. 1992.
- [CH92] J. Curdes and E. R. Hilf. "Computer programs for the analysis of PDMS-spectra". In: *Fresenius Journal of analytical Chemistry* 344.4 (1992). DOI: [10.1007/BF00322698](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00322698). [Springersharelink](#)..
- [CHT92] J. Curdes, E.R. Hilf, and W. Tuszynski. "Computer Analysis Tools for PDMS Spectra". In: *6th Texas Symposium on Mass Spectrometry, Gaspe, Quebec, Canada*. 1992.
- [KTH92b] F. Kieselung, W. Tuszynski, and E.R. Hilf. "Analyte-Analyte Interactions Influencing the PDMS-Yield; Texas Symposium". In: *6th Texas Symposium on Mass Spectrometry, Gaspe, Quebec, Canada*. 1992.
- [TKH92] W. Tuszynski, F. Kieselung, and E.R. Hilf. "Analyte-Analyte Interactions Influencing the PDMS Yield". In: *40th ASMS Conference on Mass Spectrometry and Allied Topics, Washington, DC*. 1992.
- [Doh+92] B. Dohmen et al. "Analysis on Entropic vs. Thermal Fragmentation". In: 1992.
- [Cur+92b] J. Curdes et al. "Computer Analysis Tools for PDMS Spectra". In: 1992.
- [KTH92a] F. Kieselung, W. Tuszynski, and E.R. Hilf. "Abhängigkeit der relativen PDMS-Ionenausbeute von der Konzentration der Moleküle auf dem Nitrocellulose-Substrat". In: *Verhandl. DPG (VI)*. Vol. 27. DPG-Frühjahrstagung Hannover. 1992.
- [KEH92] F. Kieselung and W. Tuszynski und E.R. Hilf. "Dependence of Relative PDMS Ion Yields on the Amount of Molecules Adsorbed on Nitrocellulose". In: *Verhandl. DPG (VI)*. Vol. 27. DPG-Frühjahrstagung Hannover. extended abstracts of papers presented at the 12th International Mass Spectrometry Conference, August 26-30, 1991, Amsterdam, p. 144. 1992.

- [Hil+93] E.R. Hilf et al. "Molecular fragmentation and formation processes in plasma desorption mass spectrometry". In: *International Journal of Mass Spectrometry and Ion Processes* 126 (1993). su25 Cf-PLASMA DESORPTION MASS SPECTROMETRY; Proceedings of the 6th Texas Symposium on Mass Spectrometry, pp. 101 –114. ISSN: 0168-1176. DOI: [10.1016/0168-1176\(93\)80075-P](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1176(93)80075-P). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TG6-44WD71-JK/2/3c91bced899e4d8020ffa319195920f8>.
- [Wag+93] M. Wagner et al. "Secondary ion emission from frozen alkanes and benzene induced by MeV-ion impact". In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 82.2 (1993), pp. 362 –378. ISSN: 0168-583X. DOI: [10.1016/0168-583X\(93\)96041-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X(93)96041-A). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TJN-470P1K5-5V/2/b7155a57654031dcaaf507c018121b1d>.
- [Hil+93] E. R. Hilf et al. "Identifikation von Stoffklassen in der Plasma-Desorptions-Massenspektrometrie". In: *Einblicke* Nr. 17 (1993).
- [Hil93] Eberhard R. Hilf. "Approaches to plasma desorption mass spectrometry by some theoretical physics concepts". In: *International Journal of Mass Spectrometry and Ion Processes* 126 (1993). su252Cf-PLASMA DESORPTION MASS SPECTROMETRY Proceedings of the 6th Texas Symposium on Mass Spectrometry, pp. 25 –36. ISSN: 0168-1176. DOI: [10.1016/0168-1176\(93\)80067-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1176(93)80067-0). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TG6-44WD271-J9/2/7b05781a08de098a6666b5751bcf9af2>.
- [KB94] Eberhard R. Hilf Knut Barghorn. "Low energy cluster impact simulated by molecular dynamics; angular distribution of sputtering yield and impact under various angles". In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 88.1-2 (1994), pp. 196 –201. ISSN: 0168-583X. DOI: [10.1016/0168-583X\(94\)96104-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X(94)96104-2). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TJN-471XN96-BS/2/193515f3de2dabffb9b33ad9f476e1e7>.
- [WTH96] K. Koch W. Tuszynski and E.R. Hilf. In: vol. 107. Conference: Swift Heavy Ions in Matter. Elsevier, 1996. Chap. Sample and Plume Luminescence in Fast Heavy Ion Induced Desorption. DOI: [doi:10.1016/0168-583X\(95\)00849-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X(95)00849-7). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TJN-44JORHG-13/2/6e2216bf1153ae651d9b440103d552af>.
- [Weh+97] M. Wehofsky et al. "Characterization of Photons Produced in Solid Films of Organic Molecules by the Impact of ^{252}Cf -Fission Fragments". In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 125.1-4 (1997). Inelastic Ion-Surface Collisions, pp. 71 –76. ISSN: 0168-

583X. DOI: [doi : 10 . 1016 / S0168 - 583X\(96 \) 00913 - 5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-583X(96)00913-5). [http : //www . sciencedirect . com/science/article/B6TJN-3SP1RV4-6D/2/252867eac3e7dd806b1614cc0a39d384](http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TJN-3SP1RV4-6D/2/252867eac3e7dd806b1614cc0a39d384).

8 Nuclear Physics

8.1 Nuclear Physics

- [W.D+77] W.D.Myers et al. “Droplet model of the giant dipole resonance”. In: *Physical Review C* 15.6 (1977). <https://escholarship.org/content/qt2zg3f80p/qt2zg3f80p.pdf>.
- [Gro75] H.v. Groote. *Surface energy of very neutron rich nuclei*. IKDA 76/10; gelbe Reihe: Insitute for Nuclear Physics, TU Darmstadt, Germany. 1975.
- [Hil63] Eberhard R. Hilf. *Über den Oberflächenterm der Gesamtenergie der Atomkerne nach dem Fermigas-Modell*. Diplomarbeit. 1963. <http://publikationen.ub.uni-frankfurt.de/volltexte/2010/7205/>.
- [HS66] Eberhard R. Hilf and Georg Süßmann. “Surface tension of nuclei according to the Fermi-gas model”. In: *Physics Letters* 21.6 (1966), pp. 654 –656. ISSN: 0031-9163. DOI: [DOI:10.1016/0031-9163\(66\)90113-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-9163(66)90113-2). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6X44-46J39J5-9S/2/3addb1e592e600251c20cae69298b2c5>.
- [Kna+66] S. Knaak et al. “Surface tension of nuclear matter from the shell model”. In: *Physics Letters* 23.12 (1966). copies at http://publikationen.uni-frankfurt.de/volltexte/2009/7202/pdf/eb_s.surface.tension.of.nucl.matter.pdf, pp. 711 –713. ISSN: 0031-9163. DOI: [DOI : 10 . 1016 / 0031 - 9163\(66\)91108 - 5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-9163(66)91108-5). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6X44-46RVM8X-3H/2/d124610e0df147ac93c056af98ebc0a7>.
- [Hilid] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Surface and Curvature Energy of Nuclei”. In: *Symposium on recent progress in Nuclear Physics with Tandems*. Heidelberg, 1966.
- [Hil67a] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Krümmungsenergie schwerer Atomkerne”. In: 1967.
- [Hil+67] E. R. Hilf et al. “Zur Kernspaltung nach einem Tröpfchenmodell mit Schaleneffekten”. In: 1967.
- [Hilg] “Nuclear curvature energy from threshold energies”. In: *Nuclear Physics A* 129.3 (1969), pp. 513 –534. ISSN: 0375-9474. DOI: [DOI:10.1016/0375-9474\(69\)90698-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-9474(69)90698-8). <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TVB-472PSW5-9Y/2/31f6ec2a41a554519397dfcfd9be874f>.

- [Hil68] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Der Krümmungsterm der Massenformel schwerer Atomkerne”. In: *Deutsch-Holländische Tagung der Deutschen Physikalischen Gesellschaft DPG*. Bad Neuenahr. 1968.
- [Hil69a] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Curvature tension and fission barriers of heavy nuclei”. In: *International Winter-Meeting on Nuclear Reactions*. Villars, Schweiz. 1969.
- [HH69] Rainer Hasse and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Influence of the shell energy on the dynamic model of asymmetric fission”. In: *Physics and Chemistry of Fission*. Ed. by International Atomic Energy Agency. Vol. SM 122/28 (talk) and SM 122/48 (abstract) and Discussion contributions. IAEA-Conference 1969, Wien, Österreich. 1969.
- [TCH a] J. W. Truran, A. G. W. Cameron, and E. R. Hilf. “Construction of mass formulas designed to be valid for neutron-rich nuclei”. In: *Proceedings: International conference on the properties of nuclei far from the region of beta-stability*. 31. August 1970. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/pub-hilf/paper/truran-cameron-hilf-1970-leysin.pdf>.
- [LSH71] S. Ludwig, G. Süßmann, and E. R. Hilf. “Mass formula for Low charge atomic nuclei”. In: 1971.
- [Hilnu] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Atomkerne in Neutronenmaterie”. In: *Int. Winter-Meeting on Nuclear Physics*. Villars, Schweiz. January 1971.
- [Hil71b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Phasenübergänge in höchstkondensierter Materie”. In: *Tagung der Deutschen Physikalischen Gesellschaft DPG*. Ed. by Fachausschuss Thermodynamik. Münster. 1971.
- [Lud+73] S. Ludwig et al. “Droplet mass formula fit”. In: *Nuclear Physics A* 203.3 (1973), pp. 627–640. ISSN: 0375-9474. DOI: DOI:10.1016/0375-9474(73)90368-0. <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/B6TVB-47197SJ-17F/2/4b0ab27a7461e7c0e501094c094a2c82>.
- [KH73] K. Koebke and E.R. Hilf. *Tafel der Massen und Deformationen der gegen Neutronen- und Protonenzerfall stabilen Atomkerne, sowie Spaltbarrieren der superschweren Kerne*. IKDA 73/19 Preprint Institut für Kernphysik, Technische Hochschule Darmstadt, Germany. 1. Ausgabe (K.K.) 1973.
- [LHG73] S. Ludwig, Eberhard R. Hilf, and Horst Gräf. “Thomas-Fermi Method for the surface of the nucleus”. In: *Int. Conf. on Nuclear Physics; München*. 1973.
- [KWH74] W.A. Küpper, G. Wegmann, and E.R. Hilf. “Thermostatic properties of symmetric nuclear matter”. In: *Annals of Physics* 88.2 (1974). preprint skipped the word ‘symmetric’ in the title, pp. 454–471. DOI: doi:10.1016/0003-4916(74)90178-X. eprint: LBL-642LawrenceBerkeleyLaboratory, USA; preprint. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/9mf1f070>.

- [GH75] H.v. Groote and E.R. Hilf. “magic neutron-rich nuclei”. In: 1975. eprint: [Institutf\urKernphysik, THDarmstadt, Germany](#).
- [TGH] K. Takahashi, H.v. Groote, and E.R. Hilf. “Nuclear Mass Systematics and Exotic Nuclei”. In: eprint: [\url{http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THEO3/publications/ebs.nuclear.mass.systematics.pdf}](http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THEO3/publications/ebs.nuclear.mass.systematics.pdf), year={1975}.
- [GHT76] Harald v. Groote, Eberhard R. Hilf, and Kohji Takahashi. “A new semiempirical shell correction to the droplet model: Gross theory of nuclear magics”. In: *Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables* 17; the 1975 Mass Predictions.5-6 (1976), pp. 418 –427. ISSN: 0092-640X. DOI: [10.1016/0092-640X\(76\)90031-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-640X(76)90031-0). <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THEO3/publications/ebs.new.semiempirical.pdf>.
- [HGT76] Eberhard R. Hilf, Harald von Groote, and Kohji Takahashi. “Gross theory of nuclear masses and radii”. In: *Proc. 3rd Int.Conference Conference on Nuclei Far from Stability, Cargese, France*; <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THEO3/publications/ebs.gross.theory.pdf>. 1976. eprint: [PreprintSeries: IKDA76/12, THDarmstadt, Institutf. Kernphysik. CDSCernDocumentServer:\url{http://cdsweb.cern.ch/record/873902}and\url{http://smallsystems.isn-oldeburg.de/publications/metadocs/ebs.gross.theory.html}](#).
- [BHM] F. Beck, E. R. Hilf, and W. D. Myers, eds. *5th International Workshop on Gross Properties of Nuclei and Nuclear Excitations*. Hirschegg, Austria. Institut fuer Kernphysik, Technische Hochschule Darmstadt 1977, 17 - 22 Jan 1977.
- [FHK80] W. Freudenreich, Eberhard R. Hilf, and K.Takahashi. “Atomic masses – comments on Macro-Micro mass-formulae”. In: 1980.
- [Hil81] Eberhard R. Hilf. “?” In: *4th International Conference on Nuclei far from Stability*. Helsingoer, Denmark. 1981.
- [GH81] G.Kirchner and E.R. Hilf. “Application of mass-predictions to isotope-abundances in breeder-reactor cores”. In: Preprint: IKDA 81/10; Institut fuer Kernphysik, TH Darmstadt, Germany. Helsingoer, Denmark: European Organization for Nuclear Research, Geneva (Switzerland), June 6, 1981. http://www.iaea.org/inis/collection/NCLCollectionStore/_Public/13/654/13654123.pdf.
- [HW81] E.R. Hilf and R. Wolff. “Gross properties of nuclear density distributions”. In: Helsingoer, Denmark: European Organization for Nuclear Research, Geneva (Switzerland), June 6, 1981. http://www.iaea.org/inis/collection/NCLCollectionStore/_Public/13/655/13655422.pdf.

- [Hilh] “Nuclear proton emission predictions”. In: *Physics Letters B* 120.1-3 (1983), pp. 14 –18. ISSN: 0370-2693. DOI: DOI : 10 . 1016 / 0370 - 2693 (83) 90612 - 3. eprint: {preprintIKDA2 / 12 ; Institute for Nuclear Physics , TH Darmstadt , Germany}. paper / 83 - 1 . pdf.
- [HP84a] Eberhard R. Hilf and Lutz Polley. In: *Quarks and Nuclear Structure: Proceedings of the 3rd Klaus Erkelenz Symposium held at Bad Honnef, June 13-16, 1983*. Ed. by K. Bleuler. Lecture notes in physics. Springer-Verlag, 1984. ISBN: 9780387129228. <http://books.google.com/books?id=KiFVcAAACAAJ>.
- [WH84a] M. Wendel and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Nucleons In Nuclei In The Soliton Model To Quantum Chromodynamics”. In: *Int. Conf. 1984 on Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants VII*. Darmstadt-Seeheim, Germany, 1984.
- [Hil84] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Semiclassical QCD-Lagrangian for Nuclear Physics”. In: *Int. Workshop on Semiclassical Methods in Nuclear Physics, Grenoble, 1984*. Vol. C6. EDP Sciences, 1984. DOI: 10.1051/jphyscol:1984606. eprint: {IKDA84/3; Institute for Nuclear Physics , TH Darmstadt , Germany}. <http://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/docs/00/22/42/07/PDF/ajp-jphyscol198445C606.pdf>.
- [WH85b] M. H. Wendel and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Generalized moments applied to Fermi-type functions”. In: *J. Math. Phys.* 26 (1985). DOI: doi : 10 . 1063 / 1 . 526919. eprint: {IKDA83 / 19 ; Institute for Nuclear Physics , TH Darmstadt , Germany}.
- [WH85a] M. H. Wendel and E. R. Hilf. “Nucleons in nuclei in the selfconsistent soliton model to QCD”. In: *Zeitschrift für Physik A Hadrons and Nuclei A* 322, Number 1 (1985). Springer-Fassung: . . isbn/pub-hilf/paper/85-3.pdf. DOI: DOI:10.1007/BF01412023. eprint: IK DA85/3, Institute for Nuclear Physics , TH Darmstadt , Germany. <http://resources.metapress.com/pdf-preview.axd?code=k028302325233143&size=largest>.
- [RH85] K. Redlich and E. R. Hilf. *Strangeness production in the region of Hadron-Gluon phase transition*. 1985.
- [WH84b] M. Wendel and E.R. Hilf. “Nucleons in nuclei in the soliton model to quantum chromodynamics”. In: *Atomic Masses and Fundamental Constants*. Darmstadt-Seeheim, Germany, 1984. eprint: {Pre print - series : IKDA84 / 11 ; Institute for Nuclear Physics , TU Darmstadt , Germany}.
- [Wen] Michael Wendel. *Nukleonen im Kern im selbstkonsistenten Soliton-Quark Modell der QCD*. Diplomarbeit, AG Theoretische Physik III, TH Darmstadt, Germany. eprint: IKDA Institute for Nuclear Physics , TH Darmstadt , Germany.

9 Marine research, offshore sailing

9.1 Marine Research, offshore sailing

- [Hil+92] E. R. Hilf et al. “Sailing Research Vessel for the Wadden Sea: A Consequent Way of Environmental Data Acquisition”. In: *Theory Group III, Department of Physics, University Oldenburg, Germany* UO-Phys.Theo.-21-1992 (1992). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234008522_Sailing_Research_Vessel_for_the_Wadden_Sea_A_Consequent_Way_of_Environmental_Data_Acquisition.
- [BH95] H. Barth and E. R. Hilf. “Solitary wave calculations for erosion strength”. In: *Helgoländer Meeresuntersuchungen* 49 (Mar. 1995), pp. 805–810. DOI: [10.1007/BF02368403](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02368403).
- [HH] Ebs Hilf and Sigrid Hilf. *Segeln im Wattenmeer - Anregungen zur Planung eigener Reisen ins Watt*. Vortrag Vereinsabend im ROYC Rostocker Yacht Club. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/rostock04/watt-segeln.html>.
- [Fre+12] Asmus Freytag et al. *Proposal to Encode Nautical Chart Symbols used in Running Text*. <http://unicode.org/asmus/ChartSymbolsInRunningText/>. 2012. <http://unicode.org/~asmus/ChartSymbolsInRunningText/Proposal.pdf>.

10 Astrophysics

10.1 Astrophysics

- [KHE] K. Koebke, E. R. Hilf, and R. Ebert. “Hyperon Star Matter”. In: *Nature* Vol. 226, No. 5246 (). DOI: [10.1038/226625a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/226625a0). eprint: <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THE03/publications/ebs.hyperon.star.matter.repr.pdf>.
- [KK70] E. R. Hilf K. Koebke. “Thermodynamics of Hyperon Stars”. In: *Pure and Applied Chemistry* Vol. 22 (1970). The official Journal of the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry. eprint: [\url{https://www.iupac.org/publications/pac/pdf/1970/pdf/2203x0/469.pdf}](https://www.iupac.org/publications/pac/pdf/1970/pdf/2203x0/469.pdf).
- [EHri] M. El Eid and Eberhard R. Hilf. “Phase transitions of superdense matter”. In: Nicht vorgetragen, da Reiseantrag nicht genehmigt. April 1971.
- [Hil71a] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Nukleonenmaterie mit Dichten von $10^{11} - 10^{15}$ gr/cm³”. In: außerdem wurde der Gruppenbericht von K. Koebke *Hadronenmaterie* vorgetragen. 1971.
- [Hil72a] E. R. Hilf. “??” In: Hoher List. 1972.

- [Hil72b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Statische Eigenschaften von Neutronenstern-Materie”. In: 1972.
- [BHM73] F. Beck, E. Hilf, and K. Maier. “Age of the Galaxy by nuclear yield ratios.” In: *Acta Physica Austriaca* 38 (1973), pp. 201–205.
- [Hil+74] E. R. Hilf et al. “Rapid Nuclear Reactions in Supernovae and Cosmic Rays”. In: *Super-Heavy Elements - Theoretical Predictions and Experimental Generation*. Ed. by S. G. Nilsson & N. R. Nilsson. Vol. 10. <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1974PhyS...10S.132H>. 1974, pp. 132–137. DOI: [10.1088/0031-8949/10/A/023](https://doi.org/10.1088/0031-8949/10/A/023).
- [KEH74] K. Koebke, M. F. El Eid, and E. R. Hilf. “Non-equilibrium nuclear abundances in superdense matter”. In: *Zeitschrift für Physik* 271 (Mar. 1974), pp. 21–30. DOI: [10.1007/BF01676397](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01676397). eprint: [preprintseries;InstituteForNuclearPhysics;THDarmstadt,Germany;IKDA74/16;1974](https://arxiv.org/abs/preprintseries;InstituteForNuclearPhysics;THDarmstadt,Germany;IKDA74/16;1974). <http://www.physik.uni-oldenburg.de/Docs/THE03/publications/ebs.non.equilibri.nucl.abundances.pdf>.
- [Hei+74] H. Heintzmann et al. “Neutron star matter and neutron star models.” In: *Z. Naturforsch., A, Band 29a, p. 933 - 946* 29 (1974), pp. 933–946.
- [Hil75] E.R. Hilf. “Early neutron-star matter”. In: *Mesonic effects in nuclear structure, Symposium Bonn, F.R. Germany, 29 Jan. 1974, p. 57 - 79*. 1975, pp. 57–79.
- [EEH77] M.F. El Eid and E.R. Hilf. “Equation of state for hot and dense n, p, e-mixture with zero charge density”. In: *Astronomy and Astrophysics AAP* 57 no. 1-2 (1977).

Neutron and hadron stars; cosmic element synthesis.

11 Diverses

11.1 various contributions

- [Hil97a] Eberhard R. Hilf, ed. *Der Fachbereich Physik stellt sich vor*. 1997.
- [Hil97b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Ein Leuchtturm an der trügerischen Küste der Physiker”. In: *Written thoughts and congratulations dedicated to K.H. Bennemann*. Ed. by Freie Universität Berlin Institut für Theoretische Physik. 1997.

12 Diverses

12.1 various contributions

- [Hil97a] Eberhard R. Hilf, ed. *Der Fachbereich Physik stellt sich vor*. 1997.

- [Hil97b] Eberhard R. Hilf. “Ein Leuchtturm an der trügerischen Küste der Physiker”. In: *Written thoughts and congratulations dedicated to K.H. Bennemann*. Ed. by Freie Universität Berlin Institut für Theoretische Physik. 1997.

13 organizing international Conferences and workshops

Hirschegg Wangerooge I Spiekeroog Jena Leer oldenburg 1-4 fuerstenlager Hirschegg astrophys.

14 academic teaching

nocite*

14.1 Academic Education

- [E.R75b] St.Ludwig E.R.Hilf. *Theoretische Physik II für Lehramtskandidaten: Elektromagnetismus*. Gelbe Reihe: Institute for Nuclear Physics, TH Darmstadt, Germany. 2te Auflage. 1975.
- [E.R75a] E.R.Hilf. *Physik und Kommunikation*. gelbe Reihe: Institut für Kernphysik, TH Darmstadt, Germany. 1975.
- [Hil77] Eberhard R. Hilf, ed. *Das Physikstudium an der TH Darmstadt*. NDB: <http://d-nb.info/970894309> Signatur: DKs 85/4363i; Bereitstellung in Frankfurt. Fachbereich Physik, Technische Hochschule Darmstadt, 1977, p. 43. <http://d-nb.info/970894309>.
- [E.R77] E.R.Hilf, Fachschaft Physik, Arbeitsgruppe Orientierungswoche, Hochschuldidaktisches Zentrum. *Orientierungswoche Physik für Studienanfänger*. gelbe Reihe des Instituts für Kernphysik, TH Darmstadt, Germany. Bericht. 1977.
- [R.H04] Eberhard R.Hilf. *Methods and Theory of Clustering -1*. Seminar for InfEng Information Engineering Students at Osnabrueck. 2004. <http://www.isn-oldenburg.de/~hilf/vortraege/osnabrueck04/clustering-1.html>.

15 personal documents